

Supplementary Material for Paper “Agora: Trust Less and Open More in Verification for Confidential Computing” in OOPSLA 2025

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This is the supplementary material for the paper “Agora: Trust Less and Open More in Verification for Confidential Computing”, appearing in OOPSLA 2025 (doi:10.1145/3763099).

A The Workflow of BTM

In this section, we elaborate on the detailed workflow of the BTM. We formally outline the smart contract’s functionality in Figure 1 and the BTM TEE’s workflow in Figure 2.

A.1 System Setup

The system is deployed and managed by an untrusted administrator, and other entities are illustrated in Figure 5 of the paper. The BTM deployed on TEE consists of three components: Task Fabricator, Task Converter, and SAT Validator. The smart contract (SC) deployed on the blockchain records verification results and facilitates reward payments.

After attestation, the BTM and the BV establish a secure channel, ensuring that the BTM only takes input from the trusted BV. Then, the BTM generates a key pair (sk_{BTM}, pk_{BTM}) , and the SC records its pk_{BTM} . This allows the SC to verify that the BTM sent a message. The SC is programmed so that only the BTM can create and update bug bounty tasks. Besides, the SC also records the measurement of the BTM (H_{BTM}) to verify attestations (c.f. §A.5).

A.2 Generating and Publishing Tasks

To begin with, BBHs request *task bundles* from the BTM (①¹). Once the BTM receives a request, it generates a task bundle $B = (T_1, \dots, T_n)$ where T_i is a fabricated or genuine task with probability Q . To generate a genuine task, the BTM randomly picks a set of constraints that correspond to a function to be verified. To generate a fabricated task, the Task Fabricator removes certain constraints from the original constraint files to deliberately introduce bugs.

Both the genuine and fabricated tasks undergo conversion by the Task Converter. Based on term rewriting system [1], the Task Converter converts a set of constraints to a series of equivalent

¹All circled numbers indicate steps from Figure 5 of the paper.

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Smart Contract
1: On receive ("Create", pkBTM, HBTM):
2:   Store pkBTM and HBTM
3:   functions ← {}, taskBundles ← {}
4: On receive ("PublishTaskBundle", msg, sig):
5:   if VERIFYSIG(msg, sig, pkBTM)
6:     HB, B, addrBBH, deadline ← msg
7:     taskBundles[HB] ← (B, addrBBH, deadline, false, ⊥, ⊥)
8: On receive ("ClaimReward", msg, sig, quote):
9:   if sig ≠ ⊥
10:    verified ← VERIFYSIG(msg, sig, pkBTM)
11:  else // censorship-resistant submission channel
12:    verified ← VERIFYATTEST(msg, quote, HBTM)
13:  HB, addrBBHBTM, reward, verifiedTasks, buggyTasks ← msg
14:  ⊔, addrBBHSC, deadline, ⊔, ⊔ ← taskBundles[HB]
15:  if verified ∧ (timeblock > deadline ∨ addrBBHSC = addrBBHBTM)
16:    pay reward to addrBBHBTM
17:    taskBundles[HB] ← (⊔, ⊔, ⊔, true, verifiedTasks, buggyTasks)
18: On receive ("UpdateFunctions", msg, sig):
19:   if VERIFYSIG(msg, sig, pkBTM)
20:     updatedFunctions ← msg
21:     traverse updatedFunctions to update functions
22: On receive ("QueryFunction", HF):
23:   return functions[HF]
24: On receive ("QueryTaskBundle", HB):
25:   return taskBundles[HB]

```

Fig. 1. The pseudocode of the smart contract. VERIFYSIG use the embedded pk_{BTM} to verify signatures and VERIFYATTEST use the embedded H_{BTM} to verify TEE quotes from remote attestation. time_{block} is a blockchain built-in variable representing the current time.

constraints [4] (for a constraint set P , $\bigwedge P \leftrightarrow \bigwedge \text{mutate}(P)$), which *always* have the same satisfiability). Note that the constraints can be regarded as logical propositions, and there is no polynomial time algorithm to determine if two sets of logical propositions are equivalent [2, 3]. Hence, solving past tasks does not aid BBHs in solving new tasks, and BBHs cannot determine if a task is genuine (i.e., UNSAT) without solving it.

For any given function F , a task bundle includes at most one genuine task derived from F . The BTM maintains a mapping M from genuine tasks to the functions from which they are derived. This mapping is concealed from the BBH as M may help BBHs to give UNSAT answers without conducting constraint solving.

Each task bundle B has a corresponding Boolean array $G_B = (g_1, \dots, g_n)$ stored in the BTM, recording if T_i in B is genuine. The function CHECKISGENUINE(B) returns the stored corresponding array G_B .

The BTM publishes the task bundle B with its hash H_B on the blockchain and sets a deadline before which only the requester can submit the solutions for B (2). Any unresolved task bundle becomes available to all BBHs after the time threshold, preventing malicious BBH from hoarding

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1 : On initialization: BTM TEE
2 :  $sk_{BTM} \leftarrow \{0, 1\}^{256}$  // signing key of the BTM or  $\perp$ 
3 : derive  $pk_{BTM}$  from  $sk_{BTM}$ 
4 : initialize  $M$  // task to function mapping
5 : On receive ("ValidateSubmittedAnswer",
6 :    $(a_1, \dots, a_n), H_B, \text{addr}_{BBH}$ ) // input from BBH
7 : fetch task bundle  $B = (T_1, \dots, T_n)$  from SC using  $H_B$ 
8 :  $(g_1, \dots, g_n) \leftarrow \text{CHECKISGENUINE}(B)$ 
9 :  $reward \leftarrow 0, \text{verifiedTasks} \leftarrow [], \text{buggyTasks} \leftarrow []$ 
10 : for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$ 
11 :   if  $g_i = \text{false}$ 
12 :     if  $a_i = \text{UNSAT} \vee \neg \text{VALIDATE}(a_i, T_i)$ 
13 :        $reward = 0$ ; break
14 :     else  $\text{verifiedTasks.push}(T_i)$ 
15 :   if  $reward \neq 0$ 
16 :     for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$ 
17 :       if  $g_i = \text{true} \wedge a_i \neq \text{UNSAT}$ 
18 :         if  $\text{VALIDATE}(a_i, T_i)$ 
19 :            $\text{buggyTasks.push}(T_i)$ 
20 :            $reward = reward + R_{\text{bug}}$ 
21 :         else  $reward = 0$ ; break
22 :   if  $reward \neq 0$ 
23 :      $\text{msg} \leftarrow (H_B, \text{addr}_{BBH}, reward, \text{verifiedTasks}, \text{buggyTasks})$ 
24 :     if  $sk_{BTM} \neq \perp$ 
25 :       use  $sk_{BTM}$  to sign  $\text{msg}$  and get  $\text{sig}$ 
26 :     else  $\text{sig} \leftarrow \perp$ 
27 :     conduct attestation and get quote
28 :     send ( $\text{msg}, \text{sig}, \text{quote}$ ) to BBH
29 : On receive ("UpdateVerificationResult",  $(H_{B_0}, \dots, H_{B_m})$ ):
30 :    $\text{updatedFunctions} \leftarrow \{\}$  // verified task bundle hashes
31 :   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $m$ 
32 :     fetch  $\text{verifiedTasks}_i, \text{buggyTasks}_i$  from SC using  $H_{B_i}$ 
33 :     for  $T$  in  $\text{verifiedTasks}_i$ 
34 :        $F \leftarrow M[T]$ ; update  $\text{updatedFunctions}$  with  $F$ 
35 :     for  $T$  in  $\text{buggyTasks}_i$ 
36 :        $F \leftarrow M[T]$ ; update  $\text{updatedFunctions}$  with  $F$ 
37 :   if  $sk_{BTM} \neq \perp$ 
38 :      $\text{msg} \leftarrow \text{updatedFunctions}$ 
39 :     use  $sk_{BTM}$  to sign  $\text{msg}$  and get  $\text{sig}$ 
40 :     send ("UpdateFunctions",  $\text{msg}, \text{sig}$ ) to SC

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Fig. 2. The pseudocode of BTM TEE

task bundles but not solving them. The task bundle is recorded in the SC after verifying the BTM’s signature (“**PublishTaskBundle**” in Figure 1).

The BBH can now fetch B using H_B from the SC (③) and work on it to produce and submit an *answer* to the SC to claim rewards, as we discuss next.

A.3 Answer Submission

For a given task bundle $B = (T_1, \dots, T_n)$, a BBH needs to produce an *answer* in the form of $A = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$ where a_i is either UNSAT result or a satisfiable model to T_i . The BBH submits the answer A , the task bundle hash H_B , and her address addr_{BBH} (to receive reward payment) to the BTM (④) for answer validation.

As described in Figure 2 (“**ValidateSubmittedAnswer**”), once the BTM receives the answer validation request, it first fetches task bundle B from the SC using H_B . The function $\text{VALIDATE}(a_i, T_i)$ returns true if and only if a_i satisfies T_i . An answer is *correct* if all fabricated tasks are solved correctly. BBHs who submit a correct answer will receive a basic reward of R_{basic} . Additionally, if the answer includes a satisfying model for a genuine task, it will be rewarded with a bug reward of R_{bug} . Finally, the BTM returns the signed validation result to the BBH (⑤).

The BBH sends the validation result to the SC. Once the signature is verified, the SC pays the BBH rewards and labels the verified and buggy tasks in the task bundle (see Figure 1, “**ClaimReward**”).

As described in Figure 2 (“**UpdateVerificationResult**”), the BTM updates the verification results on the blockchain after answer validation. The SC handles the update request after verifying the BTM’s signature (described in Figure 1, “**UpdateFunctions**”). For each function F to be verified, the SC stores the counts of submissions F that have been verified and any confirmed bugs in F .

A.4 Querying the Result

Binary users query the smart contract for verification results and compare the obtained verification counts (⑥) with their threshold counts to determine binary’s trustworthiness.

A.5 Censorship-resistant Submission Channels

We provide a censorship-resistant submission channel as an alternative when the official BTM TEE is unavailable. In this case, the BBHs run the BTM in a local TEE. The locally deployed BTM can attest its identity to the smart contract via remote attestation rather than using a signature. The only difference in Figure 2 (“**ValidateSubmittedAnswer**”) is that sk_{BTM} is set to \perp , resulting in an empty signature. When the SC receives the verification result, it validates the result by comparing the attestation quote with the previously embedded measurement (H_{BTM}) and verifying the certificates signed for the quote, thus confirming the BTM TEE used by the BBH is authentic. This guarantees that bugs can be reported even if the BTM is unavailable or deliberately refusing service.

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